

Complex Networks and Climate Action: The Role of Brokers in Effective EU Policy Implementation

Andreea Nita^{1,2}, Montserrat Zamorano¹, and Laurentiu Rozylowicz²

¹ University of Granada, Department of Civil Engineering, Gran Vía de Colón, 48, 18071, Granada, Spain

andreea.nita@ugr.es,

² University of Bucharest, Center for Environmental Research, 1 N Balcescu, 010041, Bucharest, Romania

1 Introduction

The European Union (EU) is undergoing a crucial transition toward sustainability, spearheaded by a comprehensive framework of climate and energy policies [7, 4, 5]. Understanding the relationships between nations and sectors, and how these interactions shape policy implementation is critical for effective governance [6].

In this study, we analyze the dynamics of climate and energy policies within the EU using complex network analysis to identify key actors, dimensions, and sectors influencing the execution of policies aimed at mitigating climate change between 2020 and 2030. Specifically, we emphasize the role of brokers, namely the actors that mediate between unconnected entities, as essential facilitators in the EU's climate policy network.

2 Data and Methodology

Our analysis is grounded in data from the European Environment Agency (EEA), which provided an extensive database on integrated national climate and energy policies and measures in Europe. Out of the 3,342 policies examined, we focused on 1,435 policies expected to be implemented between 2020 and 2030. Each policy was associated with relevant EU dimensions, such as Decarbonization (GHG emissions and removals, Renewable Energy, Energy Efficiency) and specific sectors affected, such as Agriculture, Land Use, Land-use Change and Forestry (LULUCF), Energy Consumption, and Transport.

We built a two-mode network through Social Network Analysis (SNA)[3], where the first mode represented the countries and the second mode represented the policy dimensions and sectors affected by these policies. Through this network, we identified the most influential countries and policy dimensions that play a critical role in the EU's climate policy implementation. The analysis provided insights into how these countries and policy dimensions interconnect, thus revealing structural patterns of influence and coordination.

A core element of our research is on the brokerage roles[2, 1], that emerge within the policy network. For each policy, we extracted data on the entities responsible for

implementing it, including public and private organizations, government bodies, and international institutions. These entities were characterized based on their role in facilitating communication and coordination across different subgroups of actors within the policy network.

We measured brokerage activity as the tendency of an actor (e.g., a country or entity) to mediate between otherwise unconnected actors within or between subgroups. Additionally, we employed the concept of brokerage role exclusivity, which captures the tendency of an actor to serve as the sole mediator between unconnected actors. This exclusivity is vital for understanding the concentration of influence and control within the network.

3 Preliminary Results

Certain countries emerged as central nodes within the network, mediating between numerous sectors and policy dimensions. For example, larger EU economies like Germany, France, and Spain played pivotal brokerage roles, not only within their national context but also in bridging gaps between countries with varying policy priorities.

Among the policy dimensions analyzed, Decarbonization and Energy Efficiency were the most frequently addressed dimensions, affecting a broad range of sectors. Policies targeting GHG emissions reductions were particularly prominent across sectors such as Transport and Energy Consumption, reflecting their critical importance in meeting EU climate targets. The Agriculture and Transport sectors were identified as the most interconnected with other sectors, highlighting their vulnerability to climate policies and their potential role in driving systemic changes across the EU. Entities responsible for these sectors demonstrated high brokerage activity, acting as crucial mediators between policy areas like energy and land use.

Few pivotal actors (both governmental and non-governmental) were found to hold exclusive brokerage roles, meaning they were the sole actors mediating between disconnected subgroups. These brokers played a decisive role in ensuring the successful implementation and coordination of climate policies across countries and sectors. For instance, agencies responsible for cross-sectoral policies, such as energy regulators or transport authorities, often held exclusive brokerage positions, bridging gaps between national and EU-level frameworks. The study revealed that entities with diverse brokerage roles were more effective in navigating complex policy landscapes. Multi-role brokers, those that held more than one type of brokerage role (e.g., both consultant and gatekeeper), were particularly influential in facilitating policy integration across different dimensions, from decarbonization to energy transition.

4 Conclusions

The findings of this study underscore the significance of brokers in the implementation of climate and energy policies within the EU. By facilitating connections between otherwise isolated actors, brokers enable more cohesive and effective climate governance. The most influential brokers often held exclusive or diverse roles, which allowed them to mediate across national and sectoral boundaries, ensuring the alignment of climate

action with the overarching goals of the EU's climate policies. As the EU continues to evolve its climate policy framework, understanding the complex interplay between countries, sectors, and policy dimensions through the lens of network analysis offers a pathway for more informed and coordinated decision-making. Brokers, by bridging these gaps, can help drive the systemic changes required to meet the ambitious targets set by the EU for 2030 and beyond. Future research should focus on expanding these findings by incorporating temporal data to observe how brokerage roles evolve, as well as exploring the potential of emerging technologies in supporting brokers in their roles as mediators within the climate policy network.

5 Acknowledgements

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. We acknowledge the financial support of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Individual Fellowship under grant agreement No 101152528.

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